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DISC2024

**Faculty of Technical Sciences
University of Novi Sad**

**Hybrid event
5th & 6th December, 2024
Novi Sad, Serbia**

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Department of Environmental Engineering and Occupational Safety and Health
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

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MARKET PRESENCE OF RESORCINOL IN COSMETICS AND ITS POTENTIAL THYROID DISRUPTION

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Abstract:

Resorcinol (RCO) is a synthetic organic compound with a phenolic structure, widely used in the cosmetic industry as a preservative in hair dyes, shampoos, and anti-acne products. Additionally, RCO serves as a food preservative. RCO is considered as a potential endocrine disruptor due to its ability to inhibit thyroid peroxidase, an enzyme essential for thyroid hormone synthesis. The aim of this research was to examine the presence of RCO in cosmetic products available on the Serbian market by analyzing product declarations. Besides, this study aimed to evaluate *in silico* binding affinity of RCO to thyroid receptors and thyroxine-binding globulin enzyme (TBG). The sampling of the cosmetic products was conducted in drugstore and pharmacy chains, including their online stores. The binding affinity of RCO for the thyroid receptors (TR α ; PDB entry: 1NAV and TR β ; PDB entry: 1NAX) and TBG (PDB entry: 4X30) was assessed using GOLD molecular docking tool and expressed as ChemPLP fitness score. 2D protein-ligand interactions were visualized using the academic version of MAESTRO Schrödinger software. Market analysis included 59 randomly selected cosmetic products. Among them, RCO and its derivatives were identified in 18 products (15 brands of hair dyes and 3 anti-acne products), which represents 30.51% of the entire sample. In the docking study, binding affinities of RCO were 41.98, 45.39, and 38.45 for TR α , TR β , and TBG, respectively, compared to co-crystallized ligand affinities of 88.89, 99.00, and 81.72, respectively. The obtained ChemPLP scores suggest moderate to weak thyroid-disruption potential. However, the visualizations of protein-ligand interactions revealed that RCO fits into TBG's binding pocket, forming bonds with amino-acid residues crucial for binding with endogenous ligand, thyroxine. This suggests the possibility of RCO to interfere with thyroxine transport, presenting another potential mechanism of thyroid disruption. RCO's market presence and thyroid effects necessitate further safety assessments of this compound.

Keywords: *Resorcinol; Endocrine disruptors; Molecular docking; Personal care products*

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